

Diel and seasonal patterns of methane fluxes in ricefields

H. U. Neue, R. Wassmann, R. S. Lantin, M. C. Alberto, and J. B. Aduna, IRRI

Methane fluxes in ricefields show distinct diel and seasonal variations (Fig. 1a, b), but controlling factors and processes are poorly understood.

Emissions usually increase rapidly after sunrise, peak in the early afternoon, then decline rapidly and level off at night. Cutting the rice shoot above the water level has no immediate effect on diel emission patterns and amplitudes, indicating that plant metabolism does not directly affect CH₄ flux. The diel amplitude of fluxes correlates with the diel soil

temperature changes. The relationship between temperature and CH₄ flux changes with crop development stage (Fig. 2). At the later growth stage, the slope is steep because of greater partial pressure of CH₄ in the soil, higher root biomass, and increased plant-mediated gas transport and capacity (greater aerenchyma volume and tiller number).

Generally, CH₄ emissions are higher in the dry season than in the wet season. If ricefields are kept flooded during the entire growing season, up to three distinct seasonal maxima are observed (Fig. 1b): the first develops shortly after flooding, the second during the later vegetative period, and the third—being the highest—during the grain-filling and maturity stages. The first peak reflects the initial flux of fermenting easily degradable soil organic matter present after flooding. If the amount of easily degradable soil C is low, no initial peak of CH₄ flux develops. The increasing capacity of plant-mediated CH₄ emission and probably the increase in release of plant-borne C sources cause the increasing peaks. CH₄ production and CH₄ oxidation over the entire cropping season will be quantified in future research to elucidate the net flux of CH₄. ■

1a. Diel variation of CH₄ emission. IRRI, 1992 DS.

1b. Methane emission during two seasons under urea fertilization. IRRI, 1992 DS and WS.

2. Methane emission and air temperature in urea-treated plots. 1992 WS, 1993 DS.

Effect of fertilization on methane emission

H. U. Neue, R. Wassmann, R. S. Lantin, M. C. Alberto, and J. B. Aduna, IRRI

Nitrogen, although crucial in achieving high yields in wetland rice, is the most deficient nutrient in the ecosystem. Most farmers apply N fertilizer in two or three splits as urea or (NH₄)₂SO₄. Part of the fertilizer is incorporated into the soil during the final land preparation stage or broadcast shortly after planting. The remainder is applied at midtillering and at panicle initiation.

The effects of N fertilization on CH₄ production and emission are inconsistent. The complex interrelationships between fertilization and biochemistry of flooded soils, plant growth, and CH₄ fluxes, however, still need to be elucidated.

We evaluated the effects of different N fertilizers and modes of fertilizer

1. Methane emission rates, IRRI, 1992 DS.

2a. Methane emission under two N sources. IRRI, 1992 WS.

2b. Methane emission from ricefields under two sources of organic matter. 1992 WS.

application on CH₄ emission. Improved plant and root growth in CH₄-enriched soil layers—as a result of fertilization—will obviously increase CH₄ emission.

Methane emissions were similar regardless of application method (Fig. 1) at rates of 90 kg N/ha in the wet season (WS) and 120 kg N/ha in the dry season

(DS). Differences in fluxes were not significant between additions of (NH₄)₂SO₄ and urea.

When organic amendments are added to flooded soils, CH₄ production and emission are increased by lowering the Eh and providing more C sources. Adding 5 t rice straw/ha increased CH₄ emission tenfold compared with mineral fertilizers (Fig. 2a). Quality and quantity of added organic materials influence CH₄ formation. Green manure incorporation showed higher CH₄ emission than did adding rice straw (Fig. 2b). Green manure has a C-N ratio of 10 compared with 60 for rice straw.

Because organic substrates are added during the preflooding period before transplanting, the initial emission peak may be missed if CH₄ fluxes are monitored only during crop growth. Small differences in sources of C and its fermentation highly affect emission patterns and emission levels. ■

Effect of cultural practices on methane emission

H. U. Neue, R. Wassmann, R. S. Lantin, M. C. Alberto, and J. B. Aduna, IRRI

Cultural and agronomic practices have been developed to suit the physical, biological, and socioeconomic conditions of the different rice-growing regions and environments. While the effects of agronomic practices on rice growth and yield are well-documented, their relationships to CH₄ emission are not well-established.

Water control is one of the most important factors in rice production. Short aeration periods at tillering and at heading may improve yield in irrigated rice. A constant water level is maintained during the growing season except where mid-season drying is practiced. Large portions of CH₄ formed in an anaerobic soil may remain trapped while the soil is flooded. Entrapped CH₄ may be oxidized when the floodwater is drained during the rice-growing season or when the soil dries at the end of the season. But a lot of the entrapped CH₄ escapes into the atmosphere immediately after the flood-water recedes and macropores become aerated (Fig. 1).